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IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
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MUNDARIJA

Omborxonada wms tizimidan foydalanishni afzalliklari.....	16
G'ofurov Shoxjaxon Abdumajit o'g'li, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich	
Интеграция проектного офиса в корпоративную структуру строительной компании, работающей по ерс-контрактам.....	21
Махмудов Сардор Козим угли	
Investition muhit va unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlili	24
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyati to'g'risidagi itimoiy-iqtisodiy qarashlar tahlili.....	27
Abduvohidov Behzod XXX	
Tijorat banklarida kredit portfelini boshqarishning asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	30
Jo'rayev Eldor Berdibekovich	
O'zbekistonda davlat budjetini kupaytirishda soliqlarni ahamiyati.....	34
Karimova Gulbahor Normurodovna	
Dunyo oziq-ovqat bozorining dinamik rivojlanishidagi o'zgarishlar, qiyinchiliklar va ularning yechimlari	36
Tolipova Baxtigul Farxodovna	
Исследование тепловых и диффузионных процессов при азотировании зубчатых колес в вакуумной среде	39
Жасурбек Юлдашбоевич Холмирзаев	
Axborot tizimlaridan foydalangan holda tashkilotni boshqarish bo'yicha qarorlar qabul qilishni takomillashtirish	49
Xujamova Shahrizoda Otabek Qizi	
Sanoat sektorida dekarbonizatsiya va qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalaridan foydalanish strategiyalari	52
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Sanoat rivojlanishini ekonometrik modellashtirish (Surxondaryo viloyati misolida)	56
Xalmuratov Zakirjan Mekkamovich	
"Yashil iqtisodiyot" – barqaror taraqqiyot omili.....	58
Lapasova Kamola Farhod qizi	
Umumta'lim maktablarida informatika fanini o'qitishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	60
Raxmonov Baxtiyor Azzamovich	
"Makroiqtisodiy masalalarni yechishda matematik modellarning ahamiyati"	63
Abdiraimov Abbas Xolmurod O'g'li	
Moda marketingida iste'molchilarning ichki ehtiyojlari va xulq-atvoriga asoslangan yondashuvlar	67
Tuxtaeva Oydiyoy Normamatovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida standartlashtirish siyosatida xalqaro tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlik tahlili	72
Raximov Ilyos Muydinovich	
Tijorat banklarida omonatlarni jalb qilishda mijoz sodiqligini oshirishga qaratilgan innovatsion yondashuvlar	75
Raximov Shoxrux Furqatovich	
Raqamli bank xizmatlarida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning istiqbollari va xavfsizlik masalalari.....	78
Erdonayev Aliqul Xalimovich	
Ta'minot zanjirini optimallashtirish yo'llari.....	82
Matkarimova Umida Alisher qizi, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich	
The role of global value chains in international trade competition.....	85
Rakhmonova Dildora Ergash Qizi	
Электронная коммерция в узбекистане: государственные стратегии, технологический прогресс и барьеры развития.....	88
Махаммадалиева Муслимахон Шерали Кизи	

Modernization of the social protection system through digital technologies and innovative approaches.....90
Abduzoirov Mukhiddin Umidjon ugli, Quدراتov Inomjon Nemat ugli

MODERNIZATION OF THE SOCIAL PROTECTION SYSTEM THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

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Abstract: In the modern era, countries are increasingly integrating digital technologies and innovative solutions into their social protection systems to improve efficiency, transparency, and fairness. Uzbekistan has embarked on a comprehensive modernization process that includes institutional reforms, digital platforms, and targeted services for vulnerable groups. This paper explores the country's efforts to enhance the management and delivery of social protection through the establishment of new agencies, the development of centralized information systems, and the application of social innovation. Key digital tools such as the Unified Social Protection Register, the E-Case platform, and the Social Card system are assessed in terms of their functionality, benefits, and outcomes. The findings suggest that Uzbekistan's reforms have improved service delivery, reduced bureaucracy, and strengthened the targeting of social assistance. The paper also highlights capacity-building efforts and outlines the challenges associated with digital transformation in the social sector.

Key words: digital technologies, social protection, innovation, e-governance, Uzbekistan, social card, E-Case, Unified Social Protection Register, institutional reform, service delivery.

Annotatsiya: Zamonaviy davrda mamlakatlar o'zlarining ijtimoiy himoya tizimlariga raqamli texnologiyalar va innovatsion yechimlarni joriy etishni tobora ko'proq amalga oshirmoqda, bu esa samaradorlik, shaffoflik va adolatni oshirishga yordam beradi. O'zbekiston keng ko'lamli modernizatsiya jarayoniga kirishdi, bu jarayon institutlar islohoti, raqamli platformalar va zaif guruhlarga mo'ljallangan xizmatlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu maqolada mamlakatning ijtimoiy himoya boshqaruvi va xizmatlarini yaxshilash bo'yicha amalga oshirilgan harakatlar, yangi agentliklarning tashkil etilishi, markazlashgan ma'lumotlar tizimlarining rivojlanishi va ijtimoiy innovatsiyalarni qo'llash ko'rib chiqilgan. Bunday asosiy raqamli vositalar, masalan, Yagona Ijtimoiy Himoya Reestri, E-Case platformasi va Ijtimoiy karta tizimi ularning funktsionalligi, foydalari va natijalari nuqtai nazaridan baholangan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, O'zbekistondagi islohotlar xizmatlarni taqdim etishni yaxshilagan, byurokratiyani kamaytirgan va ijtimoiy yordamni aniqroq taqdim etishni kuchaytirgan. Maqolada shuningdek, salohiyatni oshirishga qaratilgan sa'y-harakatlar va ijtimoiy sohada raqamli transformatsiya bilan bog'liq muammolar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli texnologiyalar, ijtimoiy himoya, innovatsiyalar, elektron boshqaruv, O'zbekiston, ijtimoiy karta, E-Case, Yagona ijtimoiy himoya reestri, institutlar islohoti, xizmatlarni taqdim etish.

Аннотация: В современную эпоху страны все активнее интегрируют цифровые технологии и инновационные решения в свои системы социального обеспечения для повышения эффективности, прозрачности и справедливости. Узбекистан приступил к всестороннему процессу модернизации, который включает институциональные реформы, цифровые платформы и целевые услуги для уязвимых групп. В статье рассматриваются усилия страны по улучшению управления и предоставления социальных услуг через создание новых агентств, развитие централизованных информационных систем и применение социальных инноваций. Оценены ключевые цифровые инструменты, такие как Единый реестр социального обеспечения, платформа E-Case и система Социальной карты, с точки зрения их функциональности, преимуществ и результатов. Результаты исследования показывают, что реформы в Узбекистане улучшили предоставление услуг, сократили бюрократию и укрепили нацеливание социальной помощи. В статье также подчеркиваются усилия по развитию потенциала и описываются проблемы, связанные с цифровой трансформацией в социальной сфере.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, социальное обеспечение, инновации, электронное управление, Узбекистан, социальная карта, E-Case, Единый реестр социального обеспечения, институциональная реформа, предоставление услуг.

INTRODUCTION

In response to the evolving social and economic demands of the 21st century, many nations are rethinking and upgrading their social protection systems to ensure efficiency, inclusiveness, and transparency. A key component of this transformation is the adoption of digital technologies and innovative approaches. In Uzbekistan, the modernization of the social protection sector has become a priority as the government seeks to improve public service delivery and provide equitable support to vulnerable groups. This process involves not only the deployment of advanced digital tools but also the restructuring of institutional frameworks and management models. The goal is to move away from fragmented service provision and create an integrated, responsive, and transparent social protection system aligned with international standards.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Uzbekistan has implemented far-reaching institutional reforms as part of its digital transformation in social protection. A major milestone was the establishment of the National Social Protection Agency under the President in June 2023, which unified previously fragmented responsibilities under one institution. This allowed for the streamlined delivery of services and the formulation of a coherent policy framework. Within months, the legal groundwork for the digitization of social protection was laid through two laws, three presidential decrees, and over ten Cabinet resolutions. These legislative acts introduced a new management model centered on decentralization, targeted service provision, and technological integration.

A key development in this modernization effort was the introduction of the Unified Social Protection Register, an electronic database launched in 2021 to manage applications for social benefits. Previously, families had to collect up to 30 documents to prove eligibility for support. With the new system, 56 types of socioeconomic data are now automatically compiled from various government agencies, enabling rapid and accurate eligibility assessments. This has drastically reduced bureaucratic obstacles and increased the transparency of decision-making processes.

Another innovative component is the E-Case electronic platform, launched in 2023. This tool integrates data from 29 ministries and agencies and uses advanced analytics to assess the living conditions of vulnerable households. In 2023 alone, the platform facilitated the creation of 14,926 electronic case files, allowing social workers to provide over 86,000 tailored services and forms of support. The system exemplifies the use of artificial intelligence and big data to enhance decision-making in social assistance.

The Social Card system, established by Presidential Decree No. PQ-267 in July 2024, represents another leap forward in digital reform. Designed as a unified platform for managing social benefits and services, the Social Card integrates biometric data and government-provided information into a single digital identity. It serves as both a tool for citizens to access their entitlements and a mechanism for the state to monitor service provision. Citizens can apply for the card through various channels, including the national online portal, mobile apps, and local social service centers. By consolidating multiple services into one system, the Social Card promotes accessibility, transparency, and accountability.

Alongside these technological reforms, Uzbekistan has emphasized the importance of human resource development. The National Social Protection Agency has launched an e-learning platform to provide continuous training to social workers. Supported by international partners, this system allows personnel to upgrade their skills in real time, ensuring that they can effectively utilize new technologies and adhere to evolving standards of care. The integration of professional development with digital systems reflects a holistic approach to modernization that prioritizes both technological infrastructure and human capital.

CONCLUSION

Uzbekistan's modernization of its social protection system through digital technologies and innovative approaches marks a significant transformation in the way public services are delivered. The introduction of centralized information systems like the Unified Social Protection Register and E-Case has streamlined the identification of vulnerable groups, while the Social Card initiative has simplified citizen access to services and entitlements. Institutional reforms, such as the establishment of the National Social Protection Agency and decentralized "Inson" service centers, have further enhanced governance and responsiveness. These efforts have increased transparency, improved efficiency, and expanded the reach of social protection mechanisms across the country.

Despite these advances, challenges remain in ensuring universal digital access, safeguarding data privacy, and building digital literacy among both service providers and recipients. Addressing these issues is essential to maintaining equity and inclusiveness in the evolving social protection landscape. Nevertheless, Uzbekistan's experience offers valuable lessons for other countries seeking to modernize their welfare systems in line with global best practices. The ongoing reforms contribute to the realization of broader development objectives, including poverty reduction, social justice, and sustainable economic growth.

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